

SCHOOL HEADS' AUTHORITY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND EMPOWERMENT AS FUNCTIONS OF SCHOOL PERFORMANCE

Mark Christian L. Lapuz, MAEd¹, Elvira S. Pecajas, EdD²

School of Graduate Studies
Biliran Province State University

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6701039>

Published Date: 23-June-2022

Abstract: This study generally aimed to determine the relationship between authority, accountability, and empowerment of school heads and the performance level of schools in Leyte Districts of Leyte Division during the school year 2020-2021.

Utilizing the descriptive-correlational research design, this study elicited data from the 28 school heads across Leyte Districts I and II.

Based on the findings of the study, most of the school heads in Leyte I and II Districts were teacher-in-charge, completed academic requirements (CAR) in master's degree, have five years and below experience as school heads, and have attended training in the division level. Further, the school heads have a very satisfactory level of authority, an outstanding level of accountability, and an outstanding level of empowerment. It was also found that most of the schools in Leyte I and II Districts have better performance based on the assessment tool of the School-Based Management (SBM) level of practice by the Department of Education. Nevertheless, it was found that there is no significant relationship between the profile of school heads and the school's performance level. Likewise, there is no significant relationship between the performance level of the school and the school heads' level of authority, accountability, and empowerment.

On account of the results of the study, the school heads' level of authority was very satisfactory, while their levels of accountability and empowerment were outstanding. Hence, the researcher came up with a conclusion that the levels of authority, accountability, and empowerment of school heads did not affect the performance level of schools in Leyte Districts.

It is thus recommended that the district heads may provide technical assistance to school heads on the appropriate approaches for higher school performance management (SBM) level.

Keywords: school heads, higher school performance management, authority, accountability.

1. INTRODUCTION

School heads are the persons in authority who manage the school and are considered the pillars of the educational system. Along with their authority, they are accountable for the outcomes of the school operations, programs, and projects.

As stated in the Republic Act No. 9155, the school heads shall have the Authority, Responsibility, and Accountability in managing all school affairs. They are accountable for the pupils' learning outcomes, teachers' personal and professional development, establishing a conducive learning environment and maintaining networking and linkages of both internal

and external stakeholders, and so as the performance of the school. Thus, the success and failure of the school depends on the kind of school head it has.

With this, Cerna (2014) wrote that the school head has a great impact to the learners' and teachers' performance and so as the school performance as a whole. Hence, it is vital that school heads possess good qualities as leaders and employ suitable approaches in exercising their authority, accountability, and empowerment so that the teachers and other personnel under their jurisdiction will also work accordingly towards the attainment of the school's vision.

Moreover, the study of Gyasi et al. (2016) has revealed that the competency of school heads and how they exercise their authority and accountability affects the performance of the school and the learners' achievement. Nevertheless, Minadzi and Nyame (2016) posited that though schools' performance is determined by many factors, it is undeniable that the manner a school head manages the school is a great factor to be considered.

As school leaders continue to pull out all the stops, to lead and safeguard their schools during the most significant upheaval to education in living memory, evidence across the globe is emerging of the critical role that leadership plays in steering communities. It generated unique challenges, forcing people leaders to respond to unprecedented events at break-neck speed.

Lunenburg & Irby (2006) further said that in times of crisis, leaders are the ones to depend on to calm their nerves and forge for the path ahead, if that path requires great toil and sacrifices. Despite the overwhelming pressures they face in their own roles, school leaders have demonstrated selflessly and solidly, that their communities can depend on them.

However, the trends of school leaders have changed considerably over recent decades, in particular with regard to the levels and patterns of accountability, the nature of their responsibilities, and the extent of institutional autonomy. This has been the case, especially for school heads but has had effects for school leaders at all levels of the organization. An interest in leadership has grown globally as there has been a growing recognition of its impact on the performance of the educational system.

Interestingly, for the past few years, the researcher has been observing the school leaders in taking their roles because they want to make a difference in the lives and learning of the children and young people. He noted that leadership is not an end in itself, rather, it is a means to enable children and young people to learn, achieve, and develop.

Having limited research on the relationship of the school-based management, the researcher has established interest in determining the impact of the school heads' level of authority, accountability, and empowerment to the performance level of schools. Hence, it is in this context that the researcher is motivated to conduct this study.

The findings of this study will pave the way to enlighten the school heads and those aspiring to become school heads the importance of practicing authority, empowerment, and accountability as leaders of the school. Furthermore, the findings of this study will be the bases in designing an action plan for a more efficient and effective school leaders and eventually improve the level of school-based management.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship of authority, accountability, and empowerment of school heads and the performance level of schools in Leyte Districts of Leyte Division during the school year 2020-2021.

Specifically, this study aimed to:

1. Find out the profile of school heads in terms of:
 - 1.1 position;
 - 1.2 educational attainment;
 - 1.3 experience as a school head; and
 - 1.4 school management trainings.
2. Determine the school heads' level of:

- 2.1 authority;
- 2.2 accountability; and
- 2.3 empowerment.
3. Determine the performance level of the school.
4. Ascertain the significant relationship between the profile of school heads and the performance level of the school.
5. Ascertain the significant relationship between the performance level of the school and the school heads' level of authority, accountability, and empowerment.
6. Propose an action plan to improve the level of School-Based Management (SBM).

Hypotheses

Ho₁. There is no significant relationship between the profile of school heads and the performance level of the school.

Ho₂. There is no significant relationship between the performance level of the school and the school heads' level of authority, accountability, and empowerment.

Framework of the Study

This study presents the theoretical and conceptual frameworks, which guides the researcher in the conduct of this study.

Theoretical framework. This study was anchored on McGregor's (1950s) Theories of Management: X and Y.

Theory X conveys the importance of heightened supervision, external rewards, and penalties, while Theory Y highlights the motivating role of job satisfaction, which encourages workers to approach tasks without direct supervision. The proponent further posited that the management use of Theory X and Y can affect employee motivation and productivity in different ways, and managers may choose to implement strategies from both theories into their practices.

Meanwhile, Theory Y managers assume that employees are internally motivated, are enjoying their job, and are working to better themselves without a direct reward in return. These managers view their employees as one of the most valuable assets to the company, driving the internal workings of the corporation. Moreover, employees additionally tend to take full responsibility for their work and do not need close supervision to create a quality product. It is important to note; however, that before an employee carries out their task, they must first obtain the manager's approval. Thus, school heads as managers of the school within their jurisdiction are important individuals in achieving their goals. It must be noted that the management style of the school heads impacts the teachers' performance, and the school in general.

Hence, with the guidance and supervision of the school heads, teachers and other school personnel can work efficiently and productively, according to the standards of the Department of Education. This could mean that the teachers and other school personnel become effective and efficient in their job if school heads as leaders appropriately practice their authority, accountability, and empowerment.

As further stated in the Theories of Management (X and Y), it is likely that a manager will need to adopt both approaches depending on the evolving circumstances and levels of internal and external locus of control throughout the workplace.

The theories cited were applicable and insightful about the present study. These Management Theories can be used by school heads to formulate and develop motivation and positive management styles, strategies, and techniques.

Conceptual framework. This study generally aimed to determine the relationship of authority, accountability, and empowerment of school heads and the performance level of schools in Leyte Districts of Leyte Division during the school year 2020-2021.

The parameters of this study were laid out through the variables such as: the profile of school heads in terms of position, educational attainment, experience as a school head and school management training; and the school heads' level of authority, accountability, empowerment as the independent variables. Meanwhile, the dependent variable is the performance level of the school, which will be the basis in designing an action plan to improve the level of School-Based Management (SBM).

Figure 1 shows the interplay between the dependent and independent variables of the study.

Figure 1: The Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the methods used in the study, such as the research design, research locale, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, data scoring, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. This is a design that provides a snapshot of the current state of affairs and discovers relationships among variables to allow the prediction of future events from present knowledge (Stangor, 2011).

This design is deemed appropriate to be used because it attempts to describe the underlying variables of the study and reveals the degree of association between the variables of the study. Hence, it gives a better and deeper understanding of a phenomenon based on an in-depth study, which provides the basis for decision-making.

Research Locale

This study covered the elementary schools in Leyte Districts of Leyte Division during the school year 2020-2021.

There are two districts involved in this study that both offer basic quality education. Thirty-two schools are situated in these districts, where District I comprises 15 schools while District II includes 17 schools.

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (69-83), Month: May - June 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Research Respondents

Twenty-eight respondents were included in this study since Leyte I comprises 13 school heads, and Leyte II has 15 school heads.

This study utilized purposive sampling, which targeted the elementary school heads in Leyte I and II Districts as respondents of the study. School leaders and managers such as Teacher-In-Charge, Officer-In-Charge, Elementary Head Teacher, and Elementary School Principal were considered respondents of the study.

Research Instrument

This study utilized a survey questionnaire as the primary instrument for gathering the data. This questionnaire consists of three parts.

Part I elicited data on the profile of school heads in terms of position, educational attainment, experience as a school head, and school management training.

Part II solicited information on the school heads' level of authority, accountability, and empowerment. The levels of authority and accountability items were lifted from RA 9155, otherwise known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001. Meanwhile, the items for the level of empowerment were lifted from the study of Short and Rinehart (1992) as cited by Wall (2012).

Part III determined the school's performance level with the aid of the assessment tool of the School-Based Management (SBM) level of practice by the Department of Education.

Data Gathering Procedure

Permit to conduct the study was sought from the Schools Division Superintendent through a formal letter. Upon approval of the permit, the researcher sent letters to the respondents informing them about the purpose of the study. The researcher then went to the schools where the respondents were assigned and distributed the survey questionnaires. An orientation and explanation of the purpose of the study were discussed with the respondents to gather the most-needed data. Appropriate time was given to the respondents to answer the said survey questionnaire.

Because of the pandemic, there were mechanisms in the conduct of the study which were strictly followed. In gathering data, the researcher followed the health protocol as mandated by the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF) and the Department of Health (DOH). To comply with the guidelines stipulated in the IATF Resolution No. 102, wearing face masks and face shields was done properly, increasing the frequency of hand-washing for at least 20 seconds each time and ensuring the observance of social distancing.

Data Scoring

As soon as all data were in, these were collated, tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using a 5-point scale to develop the study's findings.

To determine the school heads' level of authority, the following mean values and qualitative descriptions were used:

<i>Mean Values</i>	<i>Description</i>
4.500-5.000	Outstanding
3.500-4.499	Very Satisfactory
2.500-3.499	Satisfactory
1.500-2.499	Unsatisfactory
below 1.499	Poor

To determine the school heads' level of accountability, the following mean values and qualitative description were used:

<i>Mean Values</i>	<i>Description</i>
4.500-5.000	Outstanding

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (69-83), Month: May - June 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

3.500-4.499	Very Satisfactory
2.500-3.499	Satisfactory
1.500-2.499	Unsatisfactory
below 1.499	Poor

To determine the school heads' level of empowerment, the following mean values and qualitative description were used:

<i>Mean Values</i>	<i>Description</i>
4.500-5.000	Outstanding
3.500-4.499	Very Satisfactory
2.500-3.499	Satisfactory
1.500-2.499	Unsatisfactory
below 1.499	Poor

To determine the performance level of the school, the following mean values and qualitative descriptions were used:

<i>Mean Values</i>	<i>Description</i>
2.5 – 3.0	Best
1.5 – 2.49	Better
0.5 – 1.49	Good

Statistical Treatment of Data

Data in this study were analyzed and interpreted using the following:

Descriptive statistics such as relative frequency, simple percentage, and weighted mean were used to describe the dependent and independent variables of the study.

The data were also subjected to inferential statistics such as the Pearson Product Moment of Correlation to determine the significant relationships among the variables.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part presents the results and discussion of the data gathered. These are presented in tables, followed by their descriptive interpretations. Results were sequentially presented based on the objectives posed in the study.

Profile of School Heads

Table 1 shows the profile of school heads in terms of position, educational attainment, experience as school head, and school management training.

Table 1: Profile of School Heads

Variables	f	%
Position		
Teacher-In-Charge	9	32.14
Officer-In-Charge	0	0
Head Teacher 1	6	21.43
Head Teacher 2	0	0
Head Teacher 3	4	14.29
School Principal 1	8	28.57
School Principal 2	1	3.57
School Principal 3	0	0
Total	28	100

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

 Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (69-83), Month: May - June 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Educational Qualification		
Bachelor's Degree Holder	0	0
With CAR in Master's Degree	12	42.86
Master's Degree Holder	7	25.00
With CAR in Doctorate Degree	4	14.29
Doctorate Degree Holder	3	10.71
Others (Specify)	2	7.14
Total	28	100
Experience as School Head		
Least Experienced (5 years and below)	10	35.71
Experienced (6-10 years)	9	32.14
Highly Experienced (11 years and above)	9	32.14
Total	28	100
School Management Trainings		
	f	Rank
National Level	4	3
Regional Level	9	2
Division Level	26	1
District Level	4	4
School Level	1	5

Position. As shown in the table, most school heads in Leyte I and II Districts were Teacher-In-Charge at 32.14 percent, closely followed by School Principal I at 28.57 percent.

Educational qualification. Most school heads have completed the academic requirements (CAR) in their master's degree with a frequency of 12 (42.86%). This result signifies that the school heads in Leyte I and II Districts were pursuing a higher educational qualification in relation to school management. This result suggests that school leadership calls for continuous development to become an effective and efficient school leader through further studies.

Experience as school head. Most school heads (10 or 35.71%) had been school heads for five years and below. This result indicates that young school leaders can attain great performance as school administrators. This could also mean that the number of years as a school head follows the quality of experience, which eventually enhances work performance. The study respondents who had been school heads for five years and below were said to be proficient and experts in their careers.

Akman (2016) stated that younger school principals have less experience but more idealist with social and digital skills, which can perform better in the new era of educational leadership.

School management training. Most of the school heads have attended training at the division level, with a frequency of 26 or rank 1. This result means that the respondents were updated with the current trends in school management and were prepared with the latest strategies and interventions for efficient and effective school management. However, it is sad to note that only a few had attended training at the regional and national levels.

This finding was emphasized by Hutton (2013), who revealed a positive impact on the participants' performance during the period of training, especially in the areas of confidence, collegiality, and overall leadership.

Further, Mestry (2017) findings indicated that leadership preparation and training are central to school effectiveness and school improvement.

School Heads' Level of Authority, Accountability, and Empowerment

The school heads' levels of authority, accountability, and empowerment are depicted in Tables 2-4.

School heads' level of authority. Table 2 shows the school heads' level of authority.

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

 Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (69-83), Month: May - June 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com
Table 2: School Heads' Level of Authority

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. Setting the mission, vision, goals, and objectives of the school.	4.57	Outstanding
2. Demonstrate co-ownership of and personal responses to identified issues consistent with the school's vision and mission.	4.50	Outstanding
3. Creating an environment within the school that is conducive to teaching and learning.	4.54	Outstanding
4. Implementing the school curriculum and being accountable for higher learning outcomes.	4.43	Very Satisfactory
5. Developing the school education program and school improvement plan.	4.57	Outstanding
6. Offering educational programs, projects and services which provide equitable opportunities for all learners in the community.	4.21	Very Satisfactory
7. Introducing new and innovative modes of instruction to achieve higher learning outcomes.	4.18	Very Satisfactory
8. Administering and managing all personnel, physical and fiscal resources of the school.	4.32	Very Satisfactory
9. Recommending the staffing complement of the school-based on its needs.	4.39	Very Satisfactory
10. Encouraging staff development.	4.43	Very Satisfactory
11. Establishing school and community networks and encouraging the active participation of teachers' organizations, non-academic personnel of public schools, and parents-teachers community associations.	4.07	Very Satisfactory
12. Accepting donations, gifts, bequests, and grants for the purpose of upgrading teachers'/learning facilitators' competencies, improving and expanding school facilities, and providing instructional materials and equipment. Such donations or grants must be reported to the appropriate district supervisors and division superintendents.	4.25	Very Satisfactory
13. Performing such other functions as may be assigned by proper authorities.	4.14	Very Satisfactory
14. Assisting teachers and students to understand problems and identify possible solutions.	4.18	Very Satisfactory
15. Resolving problems at the school level.	4.32	Very Satisfactory
16. Involving stakeholders in meetings and deliberations for decision-making.	4.61	Outstanding
17. Providing opportunities for growth and development of members as team players.	4.43	Very Satisfactory
18. Assisting teachers in identifying strengths and growth areas through monitoring and observation.	4.61	Outstanding
19. Introducing innovations in the school program to achieve higher learning outcomes.	4.50	Outstanding
20. Advocating and executing plans for changes, including culture change in the workplace.	4.14	Very Satisfactory
21. Managing the processes and procedures in monitoring student achievement.	4.14	Very Satisfactory
22. Addressing deficiencies and sustaining successes of current programs in collaboration with teachers and learners.	4.32	Very Satisfactory
23. Developing a culture of functional literacy.	4.36	Very Satisfactory
24. Managing the introduction of curriculum initiatives in line with DepEd policies (e.g., BEC, Madrasah).	4.32	Very Satisfactory

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (69-83), Month: May - June 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

25. Conducting Instructional Supervision using the appropriate strategy.	4.11	Very Satisfactory
26. Providing timely, accurate, and specific feedback to teachers in a collegial manner regarding their performance.	4.43	Very Satisfactory
27. Providing expert technical assistance and instructional support to teachers.	4.57	Outstanding
28. Creating and sustaining a safe, orderly, nurturing, and healthy environment.	4.36	Very Satisfactory
29. Building a community of learners among teachers.	4.32	Very Satisfactory
30. Assessing and analyzing the needs and interests of teachers and other school personnel.	4.43	Very Satisfactory
31. Ensuring that the School Plan for Professional Development (SPPD) emerges from the Individual Plan for Professional Development (IPPD) and other identified needs of school personnel included in the SIP/AIP.	4.32	Very Satisfactory
32. Ensure that the objectives of the school development plan are supported with resources for training and development programs.	4.29	Very Satisfactory
33. Utilizing the basic qualification standards and adhering to pertinent policies in recruiting and hiring teachers/staff.	4.43	Very Satisfactory
AWM	4.36	Very Satisfactory

Table 2 shows that the school heads' level of authority was very satisfactory, with an average weighted mean of 4.36. This finding means that the school heads in Leyte I and II Districts perform their roles and responsibilities regarding the authority within the standards of the Department of Education. This result would push for an implication that the school heads could perform their jobs effectively. This finding could imply that despite the many responsibilities of school heads, they were still able to do their tasks well.

As emphasized by Wohlstetter and Briggs (2014), the principal's role has been altered by the advent of school or school-based management, which has led to decentralization of control and transferring considerable decision making from the district office to individual schools as a way of providing the principals, teachers, and others more authority over what happens in their schools.

School heads' level of accountability. Table 3 portrays the school heads' level of accountability.

Table 3: School Heads' Level of Accountability

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. Prepare a financial management plan.	4.46	Very Satisfactory
2. Develop a school budget that is consistent with SIP/AIP.	4.36	Very Satisfactory
3. Generate and mobilize financial resources.	4.54	Outstanding
4. Manage school resources in accordance with DepEd policies and accounting and auditing rules and regulations, and other pertinent guidelines.	4.57	Outstanding
5. Manage a process for the registration, maintenance, and replacement of school assets and dispositions of non-reusable.	4.61	Outstanding
6. Organize a procurement committee and ensure that the official procurement process is followed.	4.29	Very Satisfactory
7. Utilize funds for approved school programs and projects as Reflected in SIP/AIP.	4.46	Very Satisfactory
8. Posting transparency board.	4.50	Outstanding
9. Monitor utilization, recording, and reporting of funds.	4.42	Very Satisfactory
10. Monitor utilization, recording, and reporting of the fund.	4.42	Very Satisfactory
11. Account for school funds.	4.36	Very Satisfactory
12. Prepare and submit liquidation reports and submit/communicate the same to higher education authorities and other education partners.	4.54	Outstanding

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

 Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (69-83), Month: May - June 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

13. Assign teachers and other personnel to their area of competence.	4.57	Outstanding
14. Assist teachers and staff in setting and resetting performance goals.	4.54	Outstanding
15. Monitor and evaluate the performance of teaching and non-teaching personnel vis-a-vis targets.	4.36	Very Satisfactory
16. Delegate specific tasks to help manage the performance of teaching and non-teaching personnel.	4.54	Outstanding
17. Coach deputized staff as needed on managing performance.	4.57	Outstanding
18. Create a functional school-based performance appraisal committee.	4.61	Outstanding
19. Establish school and family partnerships that promote students' peak performance.	4.46	Very Satisfactory
20. Organize programs that involve parents and other school stakeholders to promote learning.	4.75	Outstanding
21. Conduct dialogues, fora, and training of teachers, learners, and parents on the welfare and improve learners' performance.	4.86	Outstanding
22. Promote the school's image through school summit, State of the School Address (SOSA) cultural shows, learners' project exhibits, fairs, etc.	4.64	Outstanding
23. Conduct dialogues and meetings with multi-stakeholders in crafting programs and projects.	4.32	Very Satisfactory
24. Participate actively in community affairs.	4.50	Outstanding
25. Establish sustainable linkages/partnerships with other sectors, agencies, and NGOs through MOA/ MOU or Adopt-a-School Program policies.	4.57	Outstanding
26. Allocate/prioritize funds to improve and maintain school physical facilities and equipment.	4.57	Outstanding
27. Oversee school operations and care and use of school facilities according to set guidelines	4.54	Outstanding
28. Institutionalize best practices in managing and monitoring school operations, creating a safe, secure, and clean learning environment.	4.36	Very Satisfactory
29. Assign/ hire appropriate support personnel to manage school operations.	4.46	Very Satisfactory
30. Prepare a financial management plan.	4.46	Very Satisfactory
31. Develop a school budget that is consistent with SIP/AIP.	4.54	Outstanding
32. Generate and mobilize financial resources.	4.43	Very Satisfactory
33. Manage school resources in accordance with DepEd policies and accounting and auditing rules and regulations, and other pertinent guidelines.	4.50	Outstanding
34. Accept donations, gifts, bequests, and grants in accordance with RA 9155.	4.64	Outstanding
35. Manage a process for the registration, maintenance, and replacement of school assets and dispositions of non-reusable properties.	4.75	Outstanding
36. Organize a procurement committee and ensure that the official procurement process is followed.	4.43	Very Satisfactory
37. Utilize funds for approved school programs and projects as reflected in SIP/AIP.	4.57	Outstanding
38. Monitor utilization, recording, and reporting of funds.	4.57	Outstanding
39. Account for school fund.	4.61	Outstanding
40. Prepare financial reports and submit/communicate the same to higher education authorities and other education partners.	4.54	Very Satisfactory
41. Observe and demonstrate desirable personal and professional (RA 6713 & Code of Ethics RA 7836) behaviors like respect, honesty, dedication, patriotism, and genuine concern for others.	4.46	Very Satisfactory
42. Maintain harmonious relations with superiors, colleagues, subordinates, learners, parents, and other stakeholders.	4.25	Very Satisfactory
43. Endorse appointments, promotions, and transfers based on merit and needs in the interest of the service.	4.43	Very Satisfactory

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (69-83), Month: May - June 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

44. Maintain a good reputation with respect to financial matters such as the settlement of debts, loans, and other financial affairs.	4.54	Outstanding
45. Develop programs and projects for continuing personal and professional development, including moral recovery and values formation among teaching and non-teaching personnel.	4.57	Outstanding
46. Communicate effectively to staff and other stakeholders in both oral and written forms.	4.57	Outstanding
47. Listen to stakeholders' needs and concerns and respond appropriately considering the political, social, legal, and cultural context.	4.54	Outstanding
48. Observe the Award System and a system of assistance for teachers and staff to sustain integrity, honesty, and fairness in all school practices.	4.50	Outstanding
49. Demonstrate integrity, honesty, and fairness in all their dealings and transactions.	4.71	Outstanding
50. Make individuals accountable for their actions.	4.50	Outstanding
51. Display transparent and open management.	4.36	Very Satisfactory
52. Practice a sense of responsibility.	4.32	Very Satisfactory
53. Provide a democratic environment.	4.32	Very Satisfactory
54. Provide accurate information to superiors.	4.36	Very Satisfactory
55. Undertake tasks and procedures in line with the law and its regulations.	4.43	Very Satisfactory
56. Display fair and objective management.	4.32	Very Satisfactory
57. Manage the school in line with its goal.	4.36	Very Satisfactory
AWM	4.50	Outstanding

As depicted in Table 3, the school heads' level of accountability was outstanding, having an average weighted mean of 4.50. This result conveys that the school heads practice accountability in school operations, which may result in better school performance. This result conveys that the school heads' level of accountability is high. An implication can be drawn that they perform better in their job as far as accountability is concerned.

This finding supports the claim of Velayutham and Perera (2004), who said that accountability is a tool that ensures school principals' performance in undertaking their responsibilities.

Moreover, Argon (2015) underscores that accountability should be prioritized as an important criterion to ensure the employment of administrators with accountability in the education system.

School heads' level of empowerment. Table 4 illustrates the school heads' level of empowerment.

Table 4: School Heads' Level of Empowerment

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. I am given the responsibility to monitor programs.	4.54	Outstanding
2. I function in a professional environment.	4.64	Outstanding
3. I believe that I have earned respect.	4.39	Very Satisfactory
4. I believe that I am helping kids become independent learners.	4.68	Outstanding
5. I have control over daily schedules.	4.50	Outstanding
6. I believe I have the ability to get things done.	4.50	Outstanding
7. I make decisions about the implementation of new programs in the school.	3.89	Very Satisfactory
8. I am treated as a professional.	4.57	Outstanding
9. I believe I am very effective.	4.75	Outstanding
10. I believe I am empowering students.	4.75	Outstanding
11. I am able to teach as I chose.	4.68	Outstanding
12. I participate in staff development.	4.71	Outstanding
13. I make decisions about the selection of other teachers for my school.	4.64	Outstanding
14. I have the opportunity for professional growth.	4.61	Outstanding

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (69-83), Month: May - June 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

15. I have the respect of my colleagues.	4.46	Very Satisfactory
16. I feel I am involved in an important program for children.	4.50	Outstanding
17. I have the freedom to make decisions on what is taught.	4.64	Outstanding
18. I believe that I am having an impact.	4.61	Outstanding
19. I am involved in school budget decisions.	4.50	Outstanding
20. I work at a school where kids come first.	4.43	Very Satisfactory
21. I have the support and respect of my colleagues.	4.61	Outstanding
22. I see students learn.	4.46	Very Satisfactory
23. I make decisions about curriculum.	4.25	Very Satisfactory
24. I am a decision-maker.	4.18	Very Satisfactory
25. I am given the opportunity to teach other teachers.	4.61	Outstanding
26. I am given the opportunity to continue learning.	4.61	Outstanding
27. I have a strong knowledge base in the areas in which I teach.	4.68	Outstanding
28. I believe I have the opportunity to grow by working daily with students.	4.11	Very Satisfactory
29. I perceive that I have the opportunity to influence others.	4.79	Outstanding
30. I can determine my own schedule.	4.68	Outstanding
31. I have the opportunity to collaborate with other teachers in my school.	4.50	Outstanding
32. I perceive that I am making a difference.	4.46	Very Satisfactory
33. Principals, other teachers, and school personnel solicit my advice.	4.43	Very Satisfactory
34. I believe that I am good at what I do.	4.39	Very Satisfactory
35. I can play with my schedule.	4.32	Very Satisfactory
36. I perceive that I have an impact on other teachers and students.	4.46	Very Satisfactory
37. My advice is solicited by others.	4.64	Outstanding
38. I have the opportunity to teach other teachers about innovative ideas.	4.61	Outstanding
AWM	4.52	Outstanding

As shown in the table, the school heads' level of empowerment was outstanding, having an average weighted mean of 4.52. This result means that the school heads' have performed their job efficiency, specifically on their roles and responsibilities on empowerment that leads to better school performance. This result conveys that the school heads' level of empowerment is high. An implication can be drawn that they perform better in their job on empowerment.

This result is not consistent with the findings of Vicera and Bentor (2019), who found out that the public secondary school heads in Biliran Province were moderately empowered.

Performance Level of the School

The performance level of the school is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Performance Level of the School

Numerical Rating	Number of Schools	%	Interpretation
2.5 – 3.00	1	3.57	Best
1.5 – 2.49	22	78.57	Better
0.5 – 1.49	5	17.86	Good
Total	28	100	

As revealed in the table, most schools (22 or 78.57%) in Leyte I and II Districts have gained numerical ratings between 1.5 to 2.49, interpreted as "Better." This result means that the schools in Leyte Districts were performing schools, with regards to attaining the goals of the Department of Education, which is to give quality education.

The studies of Ibrahim and Orodho, (2014) have established that the school heads' profile have significant input on pupils' achievement and school performance. However, an investigation about the impact of school heads' level of authority, empowerment, and accountability is a novel topic in research that needs further investigation.

Relationship of Variables

This section presents the significant relationships between and among the variables of the study. These are shown in Tables 6-9.

Profile and performance. Table 6 indicates the significant relationship between the profile of school heads and performance level of the school.

Table 6: Significant Relationship between the Profile of School Heads and Performance Level of the School

Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decision
Position	-.149	.450	Ho Accepted
Educational Attainment	.139	.481	Ho Accepted
Experience as a School Head	.202	.302	Ho Accepted
School Management Training	.036	.857	Ho Accepted

Alpha level of significance = 0.05

With the use of appropriate statistical tool, the null hypothesis on the significant relationship between the profile of school heads and the performance level of the school was accepted. This decision was made because the r-value of -.149, .139, .202, and .036, were respectively higher than 0.05 alpha of significance. Hence, there is no significant relationship between the profile of school heads in terms of position, educational attainment, experience as school head, and school management trainings as correlated to the performance level of the school.

This finding verifies the research of Caballes and Peregrino (2021), which revealed that there was no significant relationship between the school heads' profile in terms of designation or position and the school performance.

Performance and level of authority. Table 7 portrays the significant relationship between the performance level of the school and the school heads' level of authority.

Table 7 shows the correlation analysis, which depicts that school performance had a marked relationship on school heads' level of authority. Thus, the decision was to accept the null hypothesis because the r-value of -.016 and .936 level of significance was greater than 0.05 alpha of significance.

Table 7: Significant Relationship between the Performance Level of the School and School Heads' Level of Authority

Variable	r-Value	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Performance Level of the School and School Heads' Level of Authority	-.016	.936	Ho Accepted

Alpha level of significance = 0.05

The result implies that the schools can still attain high performance even if the school heads' level authority is not high, or even if the school heads do not always impose a high level of authority.

This finding coincides with the claim of Juneja (2020), who said that a formal authority and power might not always be able to influence people in the desired manner to attain desired performance of the organization; since in times of crisis and difficulties, people view it as coercion.

Performance and level of accountability. Table 8 signifies the significant relationship between the performance level of the school and the school heads' level of accountability.

Table 8: Significant Relationship between the Performance Level of the School and School Heads' Level of Accountability

Variable	r-value	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Performance Level of the School and School Heads' Level of Accountability	-.102	.606	Ho Accepted

Alpha level of significance = 0.05

As shown in the table, the r-value of -.102 and .606 level of significance was greater than 0.05 alpha of significance. Thus, the decision was to accept the null hypothesis, which means that there is no significant correlation between the performance level of the school and school heads' level of accountability. This result implies that even if the school heads do not always practice a high level of accountability, the schools can still perform better.

Performance and level of empowerment. Table 9 shows the significant relationship between the performance level of the school and the school heads' level of empowerment.

Table 9: Significant Relationship between the Performance Level of the School and School Heads' Level of Empowerment

Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decision
Performance Level of the School and School Heads' Level of Empowerment	.017	.930	Ho Accepted

Alpha level of significance = 0.05

Using the determined statistical tool, the result reveals that there was no significant relationship between the performance level of the school and school heads' level of empowerment. The obtained r-value was .017 and .930 level of significance, which is higher than 0.05 alpha level of significance. Thus, the decision was to accept the hypothesis. This result could mean that the schools' performance can still be high, even if the school heads do not always practice a high level of empowerment.

This finding contradicts the opinion of Spaul (2013), who stated that the lack of effective leadership and management, such as school heads' empowerment can result to poor academic standards and school overall performance.

Nevertheless, Rappaport (2004) underscores that empowerment is viewed as a process: the mechanism by which people, organizations, and communities gain mastery over their lives. This means that employees such as the school heads must be able to make decisions and actions for the good of the school, even if their immediate heads will not monitor, supervise, and evaluate their work.

4. CONCLUSION

On account of the results of the study, the school heads' level of authority was very satisfactory, while their levels of accountability and empowerment were outstanding. Nevertheless, there is no significant relationship between the levels of authority, accountability, and empowerment of school heads and the school's performance level. Hence, the researcher came up with a conclusion that the levels of authority, accountability, and empowerment of school heads did not affect the performance level of schools in Leyte Districts.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are offered for consideration.

1. School heads are encouraged to upgrade to higher positions from Teacher-In-Charge to Head Teacher or School Principal position. Likewise, they may pursue doctorate programs for personal and professional growth.
2. Further, they may attend various seminars at the division level and the regional, national, and international levels to keep abreast of the new trends in attaining a higher level of school performance.
3. School heads may maintain or even surpass their authority, accountability, and empowerment level.
4. District heads may provide technical assistance to school heads on the appropriate approaches for the higher school performance management (SBM) level.
5. Similar studies may be conducted to look into the different sets of variables in other places or districts to verify the results of this study.

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

 Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (69-83), Month: May - June 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com
REFERENCES

- [1] Akman, Terri (2016). Younger school principals mean less experience, but more idealism and social and digital skills. *The Philadelphia Inquirer*. Retrieved from: https://www.inquirer.com/philly/living/20160427_Younger_school_principals_mean_less_experience__but_more_idealism_and_social_and_digital_skills.html.
- [2] Argon, Turkan (2015). Teacher and Administrator Views on School Principals' Accountability. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice* • 2015 August. 15(4). 925-944. ISSN 1303-0485 • eISSN 2148-7561. DOI 10.12738/estp.2015.4.2467.
- [3] Caballes, Dennis & Peregrino, Lilia. (2021). School Heads Competence and Qualifications: Its Influence on the School Performance.
- [4] Cerna, L. (2014). Trust: What it is and why it matters for governance and education. OECD Education Working Papers No. 108. OECD Publishing. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/5jxswcg0t6wl-en>. Retrieved 10 October 2015.
- [5] Gyasi, Richard Sarfo Gyasi, Xi, Wang Bao, and Owusu-Ampomah, Yvonne (2016). The Effect of Leadership Styles on Learners' Performance. The Case of Asonomaso Nkwanta in the Kwabre District Assembly of Ashanti Region in Ghana *Journal of Education and Practice* www.iiste.org. ISSN 2222-1735 (Paper) ISSN 2222-288X (Online). Vol.7, No.29, 2016.
- [6] Hutton, Disraeli M. (2013). Training Programme for Secondary School Principals: Evaluating its Effectiveness and Impact. *NCPEA International Journal of Educational Leadership Preparation*, Vol. 8, No. 1– March 2013 ISSN: 2155-9635 © 2013. National Council of Professors of Educational Administration.
- [7] Ibrahim, A.H & Orodho, A.J. (2014). Strategies applied by the Board of Management to enhance students' academic performance in National Examinations in secondary schools in Mandera County, Kenya. *Journal of Education and Practice*. Vol 5, No.20, 2014. pp.1-20 www.iiste.org.
- [8] Juneja, Prachi (2020). Authority vs. Leadership. Retrieved from <https://www.managementstudyguide.com/leadership-ethics.htm>
- [9] Mestry, Raj (2017). Empowering Principals to Lead and Manage Public Schools Effectively in the 21st Century. *South African Journal of Education*, Volume 37, Number 1.
- [10] Minadzi, V., M. & Nyame, G. (2016) Leadership Styles of Basic School Head Teachers: How Does It Influence Teachers' Classroom Performance? *The International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Invention*. Volume 3 issue 4 pg. 1983-1991.
- [11] Rappaport, J. (1984). Studies in empowerment: Introduction to the issue. "Prevention in Human Services," 3, 1–7.
- [12] Short, P. M., & Rinehart, J. S. (1992). School participant empowerment scale: Assessment of level of empowerment within the school environment. *Educational & Psychological Measurement*, 52(4), 951.
- [13] Spaul (2013). South Africa's Education Crisis: The quality of education in South Africa 1994–2011. Report Commissioned by the Centre for Development & Enterprise (CDE). Available at <http://www.section27.org.za/wpcontent/uploads/2013/10/Spaul-2013-CDE-reportSouth-Africas-Education-Crisis.pdf>. Accessed 19 April 2016.
- [14] Vicera, Christopher (2019). Impact of School Heads Management Styles on the Teacher's Instructional Competence and School Performance. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR)*. 45. pp 64-74.
- [15] Wall, Lee Ann, "An Exploratory Study of Teacher Empowerment and Technical Education in Kentucky" (2012). Dissertations. Paper 38 <http://digitalcommons.wku.edu/diss/38>
- [16] Wohlstetter, P., Briggs, K.L. (1994). The principal's role in school-based management. *Principal*. 74(2), 16-17.